

**Changing the Landscape of Archaeological Publishing
Supplemental Materials**

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1.1 Explanation of Author Order

There were three levels of authorial contribution based on the amount of time and effort contributed to the project. This includes time spent writing the paper, assembling the bibliography, and editing drafts, as well as the organizational labor of leading a collaborative paper with so many authors. Contributions are organized by tier, with author order alphabetical within each tier.

Tier	Responsibilities	Proposed author order. All author orders are alphabetical within tier.
1	Leadership of project, organization of full working group meetings, drafting of Introduction, Discussion, Conclusion, Supplemental Materials, and Reply, scheduling of draft and revision deadlines, submission of manuscript, implementation and organization of majority of the revisions and proof edits.	1. Jess Beck 2. Rowan Flad
2	Leadership of working group sections, drafting of working group sections, organizing and leading revisions of working group sections, contributions to revisions when appropriate.	3. Bridget Alex 4. Ari Caramanica 5. Andre Costopoulos 6. Nicholas C. Kawa 7. Ben Marwick 8. Christina Warinner
3	All other contributions, including but not limited to attendance at full group meetings and working group meetings, writing, and feedback on drafts of paper components, contributions to revisions and editing when appropriate.	9. Dana Bardolph 10. Lewis Borck 11. Kristina Douglass 12. Alan Farahani 13. Mackinley FitzPatrick 14. Lars Fogelin 15. Laura E. Heath-Stout 16. Scott R. Hutson 17. Matthew Magnani 18. Natalia Magnani 19. Ana Cecilia Mauricio 20. Lisa Overholtzer 21. Matthäus Rest 22. Daniel Scott Souleles 23. Renata Verdun da Silva Carmo

1.2 CLAP Working Groups

Working Group	Working Group Leader(s)	Working Group Members
Ideology	Andre Costopoulos Nicholas C. Kawa	Lewis Borck Andre Costopoulos Alan Farahani Nick Kawa Daniel Scott Souleles
Publishing Dynamics in North America	Jess Beck	Dana Bardolph Jess Beck Laura E. Heath-Stout Scott R. Hutson Lisa Overholtzer
Publishing Dynamics in Latin America	Ari Caramanica	Ari Caramanica Ana Cecilia Mauricio Renata Verdun de Silva Carmo
Publishing Pathways	Ben Marwick Christina Warinner	Ari Caramanica Mack Fitzpatrick Lars Fogelin Matthew Magnani Natalia Magnani Ben Marwick Ana Cecilia Mauricio Matthäus Rest Renata Verdun da Silva Carmo Christina Warinner
Media Coverage	Bridget Alex	Bridget Alex Kristina Douglass Rowan Flad

1.3 Author Biographies

Bridget Alex earned a PhD in Archaeology and Human Evolutionary Biology and chose to focus on writing and teaching the public. She has been an editor for SAPIENS magazine and writes for popular science outlets including *Discover*, *Archaeology*, and *Science*. She has also taught science communication and anthropology courses at Harvard, Caltech, and Pasadena City College.

Dana Bardolph is an Assistant Professor at Northern Illinois University.

Jess Beck is an Ad Astra Fellow and Assistant Professor in the School of Archaeology at University College Dublin. Before starting her current position, she held four short-term academic jobs in the United States and the United Kingdom, an experience which has shaped her perspective on academic labor. Her research focuses on bioarchaeology, social inequality, and knowledge production.

Lewis Borck started in community college as a nontraditional student, received his B.A. from the University of New Mexico and his M.A. and Ph.D. in anthropology with a concentration in archaeology from the University of Arizona. He is currently an Assistant Professor and the Horizon Endowed Chair of Native American History and Culture at the University of Oklahoma.

Ari Caramanica is an early career scholar and Assistant Professor of Anthropology at Vanderbilt University. Her previous work experience includes an assistant professorship at the Universidad del Pacífico in Lima, Peru. Her research centers on ancient dryland farming systems and disaster management in coastal Peru.

Andre Costopoulos is a Professor at a research university, and has served as various combinations of Associate Dean, Dean, and Vice-Provost for about the past fifteen years. He has benefited personally and professionally from working with research partners in North American Indigenous communities.

Kristina Douglass (she/they) is a Black African archaeologist and associate professor at the Climate School at Columbia University. Douglass collaborates with communities in southwest Madagascar to reconstruct human-environment interactions over the last few thousand years and co-design research projects that center community concerns and bring benefits to the communities who have a stake in the research.

Alan Farahani was a Cotsen Institute of Archaeology Postdoctoral Fellow at the University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA) from 2014–2018, and Assistant Professor of Anthropology at the University of Nevada, Las Vegas (UNLV), from 2018–2021. He is currently a research analyst at SciScope Solutions, a consulting group he founded to provide open-source computational tools that facilitate the entry, organization, analysis, and

visualization of data collected in the laboratory and field sciences, especially in anthropology and archaeology.

Mackinley FitzPatrick is an Archaeology PhD student in the Department of Anthropology at Harvard University. His research interests lie in early writing and record-keeping systems, Andean textiles, and the Inka-Colonial divide.

Rowan Flad is a tenured professor in an Anthropology department of an R1 University focusing on archaeology in early China.

Lars Fogelin is a mid-career academic archaeologist with research interests in India, religion, and archaeological theory.

Laura Heath-Stout is a postdoctoral fellow at the Archaeology Center at Stanford University. She is a white settler on the lands of the Muwekma Ohlone people, and is descended from early European settlers on the lands of the Lenni Lenape and Massachusett peoples. Drawing on her experiences as a contingently-employed, queer, disabled, white, upper-middle-class, cisgender woman, she uses mixed social science methods to study the demographics and knowledge production practices in archaeology.

Scott Hutson is Professor of Anthropology at the University of Kentucky. Most of his research focuses on inequality, settlement patterns, and social and political organization of the ancient Maya.

Nicholas C. Kawa (he/him) is an Associate Professor in the Department of Anthropology at the Ohio State University. A growing area of his research centers on the social practices and cultural norms of North American academic anthropologists.

Matthew Magnani is an anthropological archaeologist who works as an Assistant Professor of Anthropology at the University of Maine.

Natalia Magnani is Assistant Professor of Anthropology at the University of Maine, with faculty appointment at UiT The Arctic University of Norway. She received her PhD in 2018 from the University of Cambridge, then held a permanent faculty position in Norway before moving to the University of Maine where she is tenure-track. Her work on revivals of production in Arctic Sámi regions and other postcolonial contexts engages Indigenous perspectives and methodologies. She is also in the process of completing a manuscript on early career precarity in academia. She brings this experience to bear on questions of inequality in publishing.

Ben Marwick is a professor in the Anthropology Department at the University of Washington. His research focuses on Southeast Asian archaeology, and metascience topics such as reproducible research and other open science practices in archaeology.

Ana Cecilia Mauricio is a Peruvian geoarchaeologist and associate professor at Católica University, based in Lima, Peru. She has a PhD in Geoarcheology and a MS in Climate Studies from the University of Maine, USA. Her research focuses on understanding the interaction between climate, environment, and society in pre-Hispanic times, particularly cultural responses to climate change and the role that climate change and environmental transformation had on the development of complex societies and civilization in the Central Andes. In the last 10 years, her work has been centered on the Chao Valley of the northern Peruvian Coast, where she also works with local communities, specifically with students and teachers from local schools, developing activities where they can talk about roles, perspectives, and importance of the cultural heritage in their local society. Her work has been funded by Peruvian and international institutions. She mentors archaeology students from different Peruvian universities who volunteer in her field and laboratory projects. Since 2016, she is the editor of the *Boletín de Arqueología PUCP*, an open-access, peer-review archaeology journal of the Católica University that publishes Andean and Latin-American archaeology. As editor, she works to incorporate a wide variety of topics, more diverse authors (in terms of topics, nationality, and institutions), and to have a balance of genders as leading authors and guest editors.

Lisa Overholtzer is now a tenured professor at an R-1 equivalent university. Her scholarship is informed by her rural, working-class, first-generation background and her identity as a white, cis-gender woman.

Matthäus Rest is a social anthropologist with a postdoc position in the Department of Social Sciences at the University of Freiburg and was previously a postdoc at the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology in Leipzig. He is interested in unbuilt infrastructures, the temporalities of fermentation and the future of agriculture.

Daniel Scott Souleles is a US-trained socio-cultural anthropologist.

Renata Verdun da S. Carmo holds a master's degree in archaeology from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, and is a doctoral candidate in the Andean Studies Program at the Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú. Her research interests focus on Andean archaeology, Moche archaeology, anthropogenic landscapes, human eco-dynamics, and decolonial archaeology. As a young archaeologist in training, of Latin origin, she shares the undeniable understanding of the obstacles that many researchers face in publishing their research results, particularly taking into account the language neglected by the most prestigious journals, the high fees charged for some journals both for publication and for access by other researchers, among other factors. Such obstacles, arising from a strong socio-economic and colonizing hierarchy, are reinforced and continue to reproduce an academic elite and limited access to scientific knowledge.

Christina Warinner is a biomolecular archaeologist whose work integrates the natural and social sciences, with an emphasis on paleogenomics and proteomics. She has held faculty positions in Anthropology and Biology departments at universities and research institutions

in both Europe and the United States. Her experiences navigating these diverse academic units, securing research grants from different national and international funding bodies, and mentoring students in interdisciplinary research have informed her perspectives in this article.

1.4 Work Process

After the “Publishing Dynamics in Archaeology and Anthropology” session at the Society for American Archaeology meetings in Chicago, Illinois in spring 2022, participants expressed their interest in continuing to discuss the themes and topics that arose during the session. Jess Beck and Rowan Flad, the session co-organizers, drafted a list of potential additional authors and publication venues and emailed the list of session participants to:

- (1) Confirm their interest in participating in a collaborative paper;
- (2) Assess their availability for an initial 2.5-hour workshop;
- (3) Solicit feedback on proposed additional participants and publication venues.

After session participants responded, additional invitations to new participants were sent out, and the first full CLAP workshop was scheduled on Zoom for August 12, 2022. CLAP was explicitly written as a modular paper. Our process relied heavily on virtual workshops on Zoom to facilitate discussion and outlining of the paper and working group sections. Drafting and revisions were always conducted using online platforms where online feedback and revisions could easily be tracked and shared by all CLAP participants, with an emphasis on authorial openness and transparency during the writing process.

First CLAP Workshop

During the first workshop (attendance = 14/22, 64%), we spent the preliminary portion of the meeting discussing CLAP aims and objectives, open access options, publishing venues, authorship strategies, and proposed word counts for the various sections of the paper. We then divided participants into the four working groups (Ideology, Publishing Dynamics, Publishing Pathways, Media Coverage), and partitioned each group into breakout rooms, using the guidelines below to structure discussions.

CLAP Working Group Guidelines for Breakout Rooms

Participants: _____

Breakout Session Goals

- Begin discussion of questions below
- Elect working group leader
- Set date for second working group Zoom meeting

Discussion Questions

1. State of the field: What is the issue? What are the various concerns that relate to this topic?

2. What are the costs of the current state of the field? What are the impacts?
3. How have these problems been addressed in other fields outside of archaeology?
4. What are some interventions? What are some potential approaches that could make things better? Here, consider multi-scalar approaches—what can be done at the level of the individual, department, institution, or discipline?

Working Group Leader: _____

Date for Second Working Group Meeting: _____

Additional questions, approaches, or considerations your working group has found useful, to share with the larger group:

The last portion of the meeting was used to report upon the conversations which took place in the breakout rooms. Beck and Flad subsequently used these points of discussion to draft the introduction.

After the first workshop, Beck emailed all CLAP participants a summary of the first meeting and a link to the Zoom recording of the workshop.

Drafting CLAP Working Group Sections

During the first workshop, all working groups agreed upon a group leader and a date to meet to outline their working group section. The goals for the working group meetings were to:

- (1) Elect a group representative responsible for writing the 1200-word section draft;
- (2) Decide what issues and interventions were most important to foreground, using the CLAP Working Group Guidelines (outlined above);
- (3) Begin outlining their manuscript section.

These meetings, and the subsequent drafting of the introduction and working group sections, took place between August 2022 and December 2022. From December 2022 to mid-January 2023, working group sections were circulated to the full CLAP group on Google Drive so that all group members could provide feedback. In the interim between the first and second workshops, Beck and Flad regularly emailed working group leaders to check in on meeting and writing progress and scheduled the second CLAP Workshop.

Second CLAP Workshop

The second CLAP workshop (attendance = 15/23, 65%)¹ was held for two hours on January 17, 2023. An agenda was circulated in advance of the meeting. During this workshop we allotted 10–15 minutes per working group to discuss feedback on the individual paper sections (at this point, Introduction, Ideology, Publishing Dynamics, and Media Coverage). Afterwards, we divided attendees into breakout rooms, making sure each breakout room contained representatives of multiple working groups, to discuss 2–3 topics they felt should be foregrounded into the discussion. We spent the remainder of the meeting in general group discussion, which addressed the following topics:

- What is the best way to logically order the working group sections?
- Are there themes that connect all the sections that should be emphasized in the conclusion/discussion?
- How are we incorporating authorial positionality?
- What is the best system for specifying authorial contributions?

The meeting concluded with Beck and Flad outlining a target schedule for incorporating revisions to working group sections and drafting the Discussion and Conclusion sections of the manuscript. After the meeting, Beck and Flad sent out an email recap of the workshop and a link to a Zoom recording to facilitate participation for those who could not attend the meeting.

Assembling the Final Manuscript Draft

From January–April 2023, all working groups revised their sections, and Beck and Flad drafted the Discussion and Conclusions section of the manuscript and circulated it for feedback on Google Drive. Once all feedback was incorporated, Beck worked with Flad, Souleles, and Heath-Stout to copy-edit the full manuscript and reduce word count to better meet the specifications of the submission venue.

The decision-making process that underlies the CLAP authorship order is described in Supplemental Materials Section 1.5, below.

¹ One new CLAP participant was added between the first and second workshops, hence the shift from 22 to 23 participants.

1.5 Author Order: Decision Making Process

The order of CLAP authors was informed by diverse strategies for acknowledging authorial contributions, including natural science strategies that foreground writing contributions and leadership contributions. To finalize author order, a survey was sent to all 23 CLAP authors, with the following options available for designating authors:

- A. Author order is alphabetical by surname (all participants treated equally).
- B. Author order divided into three groups: (1) participants contributing leadership roles and writing; (2) participants organizing and writing working group sections; (3) all other participants listed alphabetically by surname.
- C. There is no author order. Instead, we publish as an authorship collective (see [University of Oregon Social Sciences Feminist Network Research Interest Group](#) or the [Black Trowel Collective](#) for examples)
- D. Author order reflects career stage, with most professionally precarious participants listed first and most senior participants listed last. People at the same career stage will be listed alphabetically by surname.
- E. Author order is decided using the [CLEAR lab protocols](#): these protocols consider the spirit of the work, the types of labor involved, and the contributions and identities of authors.
- F. Other—CLAP participants were welcomed to submit alternate strategies.

Survey results were as follows:

Strategy	Percentage	Number
A. Alphabetical	4.3	1
B. Tiered Alphabetical	56.5	13
C. Authorial Collective	4.3	1
D. Career Stage	13	3
E. CLEAR Lab Model	21.7	5
F. Other	0	0
Total	100	23

As 18/23 (78%) of authors voted for a strategy that combined acknowledging leadership, writing, and organizational contributions, and over half of participants voted for Option B, we selected Option B as our strategy.

1.6 Revisions Process

The manuscript was reviewed by three reviewers. The reviews were returned on 12 September 2023. The general attitudes and concerns of reviewers can be summarized as follows:

Reviewer 2

Feedback = 174 words. Reviewer 2 was extremely positive about the initial manuscript, suggesting only minor changes to typographical errors.

Reviewer 3

Feedback = 4,611 words. Reviewer 3 was positive about some aspects of the initial manuscript, such as its ability to concisely incorporate the viewpoints of 23 authors, its transparency concerning decisions about authorship and labor, and its dedication to identifying actionable interventions. Reviewer 3 did, however, have serious concerns about four aspects of the manuscript, leading them to recommend rejection. Their major concerns included:

- 1) A request to clarify the intended audience for the manuscript (were we writing to all archaeologists or only academic archaeologists?), or a deliberate expansion of the manuscript to include CRM archaeology;
- 2) A call for increased specificity when discussing identity and inequality;
- 3) A recommendation to broaden the literature beyond archaeology or the extremely North American and English-language focus of the initial manuscript, and
- 4) Minimizing the focus on media coverage, as Reviewer 3 felt this was an ineffective strategy for disseminating knowledge to the public.

This reviewer provided extremely constructive and detailed comments and was especially helpful in pointing to implicit biases in the framing and orientation of the initial draft. They were also adept at highlighting areas where our own citational politics fell short. Overall, this Reviewer pushed for more explicit discussion of and attention to the positionality and identity of academics. This reviewer's comments inspired conversations that led us to incorporate many new non-English language citations into the manuscript, and write a new section focused on "Publishing Dynamics in Latin America."

Reviewer 4

Feedback = 1415 words. Reviewer 4 was positive about our analysis of publishing dynamics and attention to making archaeology more inclusive but considered the overall manuscript to be characterized by "naivete" and "idealism". Reviewer 4 suggested that our attention to the incentive structure of archaeological publishing was overly cynical in its orientation, and that many archaeologists publish their work because it is meaningful, not simply for career advancement. They also argued that we focused on Research-1 attitudes to publishing, underscoring that there are many different kinds of institutions of higher education in the

U.S., that some institutions prioritize teaching, and that our overall framing was dismissive of academics who enjoyed and valued pedagogy. Reviewer 4 likewise emphasized the decreasing agency of faculty relative to the increasing power of trustees and administrators, rendering many of our suggestions commendable but also “unrealistic”. This reviewer was dubious about Open Access venues, emphasizing their ties to the for-profit publishing industry, and underscored the dangers of pre-print archives for disseminating dubious scientific information. Finally, while positive about our analysis of archaeology and the media, Reviewer 4 underscored that archaeologists have little control of what eventually gets disseminated due to the incentive structure of mass media.

In order to solicit and enable feedback from all authors, Beck created a table listing all individual recommended revisions (62 total). These were uploaded in a Google Doc, with the following instructions circulated via email on 29 September 2023, which asked authors:

to comment on the revisions, specifying which revisions we want to incorporate, and which we may want to push back against. If minor revisions (e.g. incorporation of a citation, clarification of vocabulary) are not commented upon by any CLAP authors, I will assume that we are all on board with incorporating the suggestion. I have carefully gone through all reviewer recommendations and partitioned them into individual changes (62 in total). The organized revisions are available here: CLAP Revisions Checklist. As in previous collaborative Google Docs, we ask that everyone remembers to turn on suggestions when making comments, and signs their initials if they are not logged in through a named account.

After the initial period of soliciting feedback, Beck and Flad worked with group leaders to divide the revisions among authors and groups. The total breakdown for revisions by author was as follows:

Author number	Name	Revisions handled individually, Count (Percent)	Revisions handled jointly with other authors, Count (Percent)
1	Jess Beck	42 (68%)	6 (10%)
2	Rowan Flad	5 (7%)	
3	Bridget Alex	1 (2%)	
4	Ari Caramanica		3 (5%)
5	Andre Costopoulos	2 (3%)	
6	Nick Kawa	3 (5%)	
7	Ben Marwick		3 (5%)

15	Laura Heath-Stout	1 (2%)	1 (2%)
19	Ana Cecilia Mauricio		3 (5%)
23	Renata Verdun	1 (2%)	3 (5%)

The count of revisions in the table above does not necessarily reflect effort invested in the process, and many authors not listed in this table offered suggestions and advice for those tasked with implementing the revisions. In particular, Ari Caramanica, Ana Cecilia Mauricio, and Renata Verdun invested a significant amount of effort in writing the “Publishing Dynamics in Latin America” section and working with Beck to incorporate Spanish and Portuguese citations throughout the rest of the manuscript. In addition to these efforts, Daniel Scott Souleles offered feedback on the cover letter that was submitted with the revisions, and Dana Bardolph, Rowan Flad, Andre Costopoulos, Nick Kawa, Ben Marwick, and Lisa Overholtzer offered final copy-editing and phrasing suggestions to improve the flow and concision of the manuscript.

While we had planned to have a final Zoom meeting to discuss revisions, the demands of the teaching semester and fieldwork meant that revisions were not finalized until 28 June 2024. Because we wanted this paper to be relatively current when it was published, and because multiple early career scholars were authors, making it important to publish in a timely fashion, we decided on a two-week period for authors to read the final draft and provide final comments.

1.7 Proofs Process

Proofs were returned on 8 January 2026.

Beck and Flad organized a system for soliciting comments via email and provided coauthors with a deadline for submitting edits.

In total, 12/23 (52%) authors (including Daniel Scott Souleles, Ben Marwick, Nick Kawa, Ana Cecilia Mauricio, Scott R. Hutson, Rowan Flad, Dana Bardolph, Christina Warinner, Bridget Alex, Renata Verdun da Silva Carmo, and Lewis Borck) returned 36 suggested edits on the proofs, and Beck identified an additional 13 edits.

Beck, Flad, and Marwick copy-edited the supplemental materials and uploaded them to the repository Zenodo.

Finally, Beck and Flad responded to 42 editorial queries, with support from individual coauthors on specific queries pertaining to their sections.

Proofs were returned to the journal on 15 January 2026.

1.8 APPENDIX

Non-Engagement Benefits/Risks

Benefits of non-engagement include time and energy for other obligations, like scholarly publications and grant seeking, which generally factor more in hiring and promotion decisions. Non-engagement may insulate researchers from public critique. However, by offering “no comment,” the expert relinquishes the narrative. Their research may be mischaracterized or sensationalized (Schäfer 2011), without the input the archaeologist could have provided. Moreover, the archaeologist loses visibility among diverse publics (Rödder 2011), which might have attracted future partners, funders, and students. Also lost is the opportunity for scientists to hone talking points, which articulate the value of their work to the public, policymakers, and administrators (Stojanowski and Duncan 2015). Finally, press avoidance can reinforce the ivory tower, increasing public mistrust of academics and threatening research support (Shofield 2021).

Eschewing media engagement will impact stakeholders. A potential benefit is that sensitive information or sacred knowledge might remain private. But without press coverage of research, affected communities may not be able to access the findings, which could be used to address contemporary issues. If research *does* appear in mass media, but lacks expert input, the portrayal of stakeholders may aggravate stereotypes and issues such as disputes over land claims. Likely positioned with greater privilege, the archaeologist who avoids the press shirks the burden of educating the public and shifts it onto stakeholders.

Members of the public enjoy archaeological narratives that are unconstrained by expert opinions based on evidence—hence the popularity of pseudoscience series like *Ancient Aliens* and *Ancient Apocalypse*. Such media-spun depictions of archaeology relieve audiences of the cognitive dissonance that arises when reality challenges their beliefs. These representations also create community for individuals sharing those beliefs. Of course, these portrayals sometimes include disinformation or misinformation, which fuels stereotypes (Halmhofer 2021; Onion 2022). Lost then, is the opportunity to disseminate evidence-based archaeology, which could be leveraged to address contemporary issues and attract students from diverse backgrounds. Non-engagement therefore incurs the risk of ceding all discussion to pseudoscientific narratives. Archaeological research becomes more susceptible to attacks about allegedly wasted taxpayer money, like Senator Rand Paul’s periodic tirades against NSF-funded projects (Mervis 2017).

To minimize risks of non-engagement, the researcher can interact directly with the public through events like open lectures or K-12 school visits. Archaeologists representing a diversity of backgrounds can engage in programs targeting K-12 classrooms to change how early learners perceive practitioners of the field look. An example of this is the “I Am A Scientist” series designed by The Plenary, Co. (<https://www.iamascientist.info/educators>). If teaching in higher education, the archaeologist might assign public-facing projects to their students (Begley 2013; NASEM 2017); this option boasts the added benefit that such service learning or engaged scholarship has been shown to improve student learning outcomes (Warren 2012). In the realm of publishing, archaeologists can produce social media, such as blogs (e.g. <https://johnhawks.net/weblog/>) or threads on Bluesky. A recent study of social media posting in China shows that only a small fraction of social media accounts focused on

the human past were authored by professionals, and enthusiasts maintain an outsized influence in this discourse (Ma et al. 2022).

Passive Engagement Benefits/Risks

Passive engagement helps build public trust in science and clarifies the relevance of archaeological work to broader social and political issues. This work with media is limited and sporadic, but still drains time and intellectual/emotional energy. Perhaps the greatest risk for the researcher, though, comes from having limited control of the narrative. An archaeologist's words may be quoted out of context or their name might appear in a story that presents objectionable views. By contributing something to a piece, the researcher seems to endorse its entire content.

Stakeholders benefit when passive engagement makes research accessible and raises awareness of their issues, knowledge, and experiences (Ataly 2006; Blakey 2020; Flewellen et al. 2021; Fong et al. 2022; Sebastian Dring et al. 2019; Wylie 2008). The exposure also provides names—and potential contacts—of researchers studying issues that affect communities. On the other hand, stakeholders may be omitted from the narrative; their perspectives may be stolen or appropriated by a scholar, who receives the spotlight.

Society as a whole can benefit from passive engagement because people see research results. They can apply the knowledge to current issues and understand research's value, increasing the likelihood of future support. Expert input adds credibility, while media outlets make the knowledge easy to grasp and locate through search engines and social media. When researchers are attentive to the need to be personable and to the expectations of the audience, and don't assume that their expertise will be automatically accepted, passive engagement mediated by media outlets can be particularly effective and reach a large audience. When featured on major media outlets, archaeologists and their research become visible to future students from diverse backgrounds. Yet, there remain some potential costs as the press-produced narrative may be incomplete or misleading—and seem to have the approval of legitimate researchers. Also, editors arbitrate what research is newsworthy, and this creates a distorted, partial view of the field. Publications target different audiences, so the researcher's message may only reach certain demographics.

To optimize passive engagement, the researcher should prepare for media encounters. Before interviews, they can distill key points, which should address a project's significance, ethics, and narratively-rich aspects of the methodology. Journalists appreciate descriptive anecdotes, like how you trudged through waist-deep mud to reach a site or found a hominin baby tooth among thousands of faunal remains. Providing such details, along with high-resolution images and other multi-media, can boost a pop-science story's popularity. Journalists rarely allow interviewees to review full articles before publication, but usually will share excerpts that include a source's contributions. Still, this peek may not reveal the article's framing. To avoid inclusion in an objectionable piece, ask the journalist to outline the story and its aims before an interview. For help interacting with journalists, academic archaeologists can rely on institutional press offices.

Intentional Engagement Benefits/Risks

Intentional engagement demands the most time and intellectual/emotional energy, not only to produce the materials, but also to develop the requisite skills. In the public eye, the researcher may be criticized or harassed—or lauded as an authority and public intellectual. The visibility can attract diverse input and partnerships, which open new lines of research and support. Finally, the archaeologist will maximize their control over the narrative.

Stakeholders will be harmed by intentional engagement if the researcher colonizes knowledge. Ethically crafted media, in contrast, will improve access to research findings and public knowledge of stakeholder perspectives. Through intentional engagement, the researcher also conveys their views and approachability, opening the door for dialogue with stakeholders.

The public may struggle to find or enjoy researcher-crafted materials, compared to untempered content produced by mainstream media professionals. Yet, intentional engagement creates trustworthy resources for global citizens. Showing passion, personality, and identity traits, the archaeologist can help dismantle the ivory tower and invite individuals from diverse backgrounds into our field.

Various strategies mitigate the risks of intentional engagement. To enhance quality and reach, archaeologists can publish in popular outlets, which have supportive editors and large audiences, on the order of millions. In particular, publications dedicated to public-facing scholarship, such as the now discontinued *Sapiens*, and *The Conversation*, typically have staff, resources, and streamlined processes to help researchers produce accessible and engaging content. As one reviewer of this manuscript pointed out, it is not enough to engage with the public and assume that evidence-based narratives will win out. Effective engagement requires personable and accessible storytelling that reflects on the way that personal experiences inform our understanding. One drawback to this approach is that the most accessible versions of public engagement (e.g. live conversation or educational programs) are often the least scalable, and therefore necessarily have a smaller audience than mass media provides. More broadly, archaeologists can develop a communications plan that strategizes media engagement long before their work hits the press. Perhaps included in grant proposals, the plan would be developed collaboratively with stakeholders and collaborators; it would entail collecting multi-media and contacts throughout the research process, which would go into “press packets,” materials distributed to the press. Besides working with press offices, researchers can directly contact journalists. By skimming pop-science publications, identify journalists who, in your opinion, produce accurate, engaging stories about archaeological research. When you have a journal article forthcoming, send the identified journalists the manuscript. Journalists appreciate these advanced tips because it provides them extra time to craft a story.

Finally, throughout one’s career, an archaeologist can improve their science communication skills through training programs, ranging from one-off workshops to multi-month fellowships like past instances of *Sapiens* Public Scholars Training Fellowship and the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) Mass Media Science & Engineering Fellowship Program. Through such programs, academically trained anthropologists and scientists have been trained well enough to launch careers in science

communication. Other participants have remained in academia or entered other sectors, better equipped to share research with diverse audiences. All archaeologists should work to recognize and enhance the contributions made by those who participate in engaged scholarship, and as more institutions formally recognize and adopt policies that encourage this practice, additional benefits to professional development may also accrue (Korner et al. 2020; ACC 2023).

Appendix References

- ACC [Archaeological Centers Coalition]. 2025. The ACC Statement on Recognizing engaged archaeology in tenure & promotion. Accessed January 14, 2026. <https://www.archaeologycoalition.org/the-acc-statement-on-recognizing-engaged-archaeology-in-tenure-promotion>
- Atalay, Sonya. 2006. Indigenous archaeology as decolonizing practice. *American Indian Quarterly* 30(3&4): 280–310.
- Begley, Gail S. 2013. Making connections: service-learning in introductory cell and molecular biology. *Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education* 14(2): 213–220. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jmbe.v14i2.596>.
- NASEM [National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine]. 2017. *Service-learning in undergraduate geosciences: proceedings of a workshop*. Washington, D.C.: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/24621>.
- Blakey, Michael L. 2020. Archaeology under the blinding light of race. *Current Anthropology* 61:S184–S197. <https://doi.org/10.1086/710357>.
- Flewellen, Ayana Omilade, Justin P. Dunnavant, Alicia Odewale, Alexandra Jones, Tsione Wolde-Michael, Zoë Crossland, and Maria Franklin. 2021. “The future of archaeology Is antiracist”: archaeology in the time of Black Lives Matter. *American Antiquity* 86(2): 224–243. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aaq.2021.18>.
- Fong, Kelly N. 方少芳, Laura W. Ng 伍穎華, Jocelyn Lee 李紫瑄, Veronica L. Peterson 孫美華, and Barbara L. Voss. 2022. Race and racism in archaeologies of Chinese American communities. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 51(1): 233–250. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-041320-014548>.
- Halmhofer, Stephanie. 2021. Did aliens build the pyramids? And other racist theories. *Sapiens*. <https://www.sapiens.org/archaeology/pseudoarchaeology-racism/> (accessed 15 January 2026).
- Korner, Barbara O., Charles O’Connor, Christopher Marks and Kevin Hamilton. 2020. Guidance for rewarding and recognizing community-engaged scholarship in the arts. Report commissioned by big ten arts administrators. https://www.a2ru.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Big-Ten_Evaluating-Community-Engagement.pdf (accessed March 11, 2023).
- Ma, Mitchell, Chuya Hoshino, Yufeng Sun, and Hailin Yi. 2022. Sharing authority and participation? Representation of archaeology on Chinese social media. Paper presented at the Workshop on the History and Practice of Archaeology in China, Oxford University, August 22–24.
- Mervis, Jeffrey. 2017. Rand Paul takes a poke at U.S. peer-review panels. *Science*. <https://www.science.org/content/article/rand-paul-takes-poke-us-peer-review-panels> (accessed January 15, 2026).
- Onion, Rebecca. 2022. The ancient absurdities of Ancient Apocalypse. *Slate*. <https://slate.com/culture/2022/11/ancient-apocalypse-graham-hancock-netflix-theory-explained.html> (accessed January 15, 2026).
- Rödder, Simone. 2011. Science and the mass media—‘medialization’ as a new perspective on an intricate relationship. *Sociology Compass* 5(9): 834–845. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2011.00410.x>.
- Schäfer, Mike S. 2011. Sources, characteristics and effects of mass media communication on science: a review of the literature, current trends and areas for future research. *Sociology Compass* 5/6: 399–412. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2011.00373.x>.
- Sebastian Dring, Katherine, Stephen W. Silliman, Natasha Gambrell, Shianne Sebastian and Ralph Sebastian Sidberry. 2019. Authoring and authority in Eastern Pequot community

- heritage and archaeology. *Archaeologies* 15(3): 352–370. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11759-019-09377-4>.
- Shofield, John. 2021. Six reasons to save archaeology from funding cuts. *Sapiens*. <https://www.sapiens.org/archaeology/reasons-to-save-archaeology/> (accessed January 15, 2026).
- Stojanowski, Christopher M., and William N. Duncan. 2015. Engaging bodies in the public imagination: bioarchaeology as social science, science, and humanities. *American Journal of Human Biology* 27:51–60. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajhb.22522>.
- Warren, Jami L. 2012. Does service-learning increase student learning?: A meta-analysis. *Michigan Journal of Community Service Learning* 18(2): 56–61.
- Wylie, Alison. 2008. The integrity of narratives: deliberative practice, pluralism, and multivocality. In *Evaluating multiple narratives: beyond nationalist, colonialist, imperialist archaeologies*, Junko Habu, Clare Fawcett, and John M. Matsunaga, eds. Pp. 201–212. New York: Springer.